

ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS' EMOTIONAL STABILITY, PARENTING STYLE AND TEACHING METHOD ON STUDENT LEARNING ACHIEVEMENT: A CASE STUDY OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT IN JAKARTA

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ABSTRACT

Learning process is fundamental in the educational process where teacher has important role in the learning activities. The capability, duties and responsibilities of teachers will be studied here. The teaching method is also reviewed in this study that linked too many factors to get the best possible strategy to overcome the obstacles encountered in the implementation of teaching and learning activities.

This study tries to complete the teaching method with the home parenting style and their emotional stability toward the student encouragement and class achievement. This is quantitative descriptive study with purposive sampling. The respondents were elementary school students in South Jakarta Indonesia.

The analysis results showed that student emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method simultaneously has significant influence to increase student achievement in elementary school students.

Keyword: emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method

INTRODUCTION

One aspect that determines the success of student learning is the improvement in their learning process. It is a core of the educational process that teacher must aware on delivering the lessons, especially in motivating students to learn. Brookhart (2001) argued that the main criterion of successful learning is the process in the class evaluation such as formative and summative evaluation at the end of semester testing (Wessels, 2009). The process during the class is the duties and responsibilities of the teachers which impact on the students learning about the lesson subjects. Teacher must set the best possible strategy to overcome the obstacles encountered in the learning activities (Brush, 2007) especially for the subject which need higher concentration such as exact and science. In addition, the student emotional stability has been lack of attention and their effect on the learning achievement (Piccoli, 2001).

Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2007 reported that the quality of mathematics education in Indonesia still less satisfactory. The survey of 2007 showed that the mastery of math score among Indonesian youth students is lower than average participating countries. Indonesia scored 397 from average of 500. It put Indonesia ranked 36 out of 46 countries. Compared to Singapore and Malaysia, Indonesia is far behind them. Singapore and Malaysia are third and twentieth in mathematics, respectively (Mullis, Martin, & Foy, 2008, p.35).

Khatri (2002) stated that science and mathematics tend to be a nightmare for students. Both lessons tend to impact of boring and confusion in the subject apprehension. In addition, the lack of teacher creativity and tech savvy also impact to student difficulties to memorize and

understand (Aikenhead, 2005). Therefore, the teaching methodology must be evaluated especially on how it is integrated with the learning environment (Henderson, 2002). Blaming teacher itself in the school will not bring better solution. Therefore, finding the other aspect is also important especially from the psychological and education perspectives.

Several studies suggested that student has many aspects which impact on their learning achievement such as personality and family situation (Schwartz, 2001; Aikenhead, 2005). Family and home atmosphere can impact on their achievement (Schwartz, 2001). Therefore, it is important to understand how the parent can support their children and fostering encouragement of their learning achievement (Spera, 2005).

Parenting style of children varies of their background region, social status, ethnicity and religion which affect the students' learning ability.

According to Schwartz (2001) and Dornyei (2003), student at junior high school is a child in their golden age that can maximize its potential if given a good stimulus. There are two stimuli, e.g., internal and external stimulus. Internal stimuli in their learning process were interests, personal circumstances and balanced emotion (Khatri, 2002). Whereas, external stimulus were family, school, site conditions, lighting, weather and time. Both stimuli were mixed together to impact the student achievement.

If the teacher gives asynchronous learning model, e.g., lesson content, unregulated learning timing, poor learning methodology, and unsuitable homework task (Schwartz, 2001; Aikenhead, 2005), it will influence the student's psychic and internal emotion which drives them into more fluctuated emotion and finally impact on lower achievement (Dornyei, 2003).

This showed us that fluctuated emotion can play an important role in achieving their class process. As a response, teacher must map the disturbance of feelings in the school environment, such as sadness, anger, and frustration. Therefore, teachers and parents must join their role for to improve the student achievement.

Based on the explanation above, it is proposed several research questions as below.

1. Is there a positive influence on students' emotional stability to increase student achievement in math and science?
2. Is there any influence of parenting style to increase student achievement in math and science?
3. How the teaching method can increase student achievement in math and science?
4. Is there a simultaneously positive influence of students' emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method to increase student achievement in math and science?

Learning Defined

Education is a process to support individuals to live and grow through formal, non-formal and informal institution (Alheit, 2002). Education is the process of learning to lead to positive changes (Boud, 2000). Therefore, the more one learns, it will further increase the knowledge. In addition, the experience and understanding of things also affect the way a person behaves, thinks, and acts.

Bryk (2002) argued that education has five elements, e.g., students, principals, teachers, practice, school facilities, and parents. Education in schools leads students to acquire the knowledge, understanding, skills, attitudes and values which bring impact on the student development.

Integration of education from home to school is a must to know the variables impacting student achievement and learning environment (Papastergiou, 2009).

Parenting Style

Hersey and Blanchard (1978) stated that the concept of parenting style had been adopted from the theory of situational leadership, which in turn also completing the views on parenting terminology where parent as informal leader and their child as the member of a family. They stated that parenting style is situational, meaning that situational factors, e.g., willingness and ability of children will impact on the student ability to understand and do something (Hersey and Blanchard, 1978). It means that children are willing to do something in the environment which can support them. Such place is introduced at first in their home as the suitable learning environment which is important as the basic start to build their confidence and positive thinking about themselves and public acceptance.

Emotion Defined

Emotion is the student response to a physical stimulus especially from the basic need of food, temperature, and noise (Jones, 2014). If these needs are met, individuals can feel excited, happy, being loved and being motivated. But if they lack of the aspects, they will expand their responsive behavior e.g. irritating, angry, scared, worried, jealous, anxious and sad (Cole, 1963). Fonagy (2004) argued that emotion is the inner experience that affecting the whole personality. In the life development, the student emotion is influenced by fostering and inhibiting experience from their environment. Campos (2004) also showed that the children emotional toward certain stimulus will affect the physical and mental processes to adjust to new reality. In addition, strong emotions will help them to developing impulsive manner. This blocks them to develop rational logic. However, impulsive manner is suitable for student to learn music and art, but not rational logic ability.

Emotional Stability Defined

Buss (2014) showed that emotion must be developed synchronously with rational logic in order the student can adjust to class environment. Therefore, how teacher can develop suitable stimuli will impact on how student can adapt to the new experience especially in the classroom (Löckenhoff, (2004). If teacher implement and adapt conflicted stimulus, student potentially express the stress and emotionally disturbed. Worse, in mathematics lessons, sometimes the teachers raised situations full of punishment that impact on the student emotional stability (Cosmides, 2000). Therefore, teacher must explain how their student can get through emotional maturity in the learning process especially in mathematics and science (Izard, 2013). In both lessons, emotions can arise if they face such difficult situation. Therefore, teacher must find the way to keep the student emotional stability. This is supported by Mayer (2006) that everybody can build their emotional stability and influences other to become calm and stable. In class context, inability of teacher to nurture the student emotional stability will drive student to be quickly distracted by fluctuated stimuli which drive the student emotion and prevent the student to understand well the lessons.

Mathematics Defined

Mathematics or so-called math is a branch of organized systematic learning system involving numbers and logic. Math is also linked to other sciences, e.g., Physics, Chemistry, and other exact lessons subjects. According to Soejadi (2000) math term derived from the Greek word meaning *manthanein*, *mathein* or studying. This word has a close relationship with the Sanskrit word, *Medha* or *widya* which means focus or intelligence. In the Dutch language, mathematics called *Yag wiskunde* means the science of learning which similar with the

meaning of the word *mathein* in mathematics. Etymologically, math means knowledge gained by

Reasoning and ratio through realistic observation or experiment (Soejadi, 2000).

Teaching Method

Teaching is a complex and complicated process. It is a process of organizing information and relevant information source through teaching methods and approaches (Ramsden, 2003). The approach must be suitable in order the students can understand the meaning of the material presented by the teacher. It means that how teacher understand the process will impact on the student learning achievement (Papp, 2003). As class facilitator, teacher must provide guidance or assistance to students and also monitor the learning progress and open the communication so that students can expose their attention to the stimuli in the class.

According to Ramsden (2003), teacher role in the learning process need suitable interactions and interrelationships between teachers and students. Teacher must keep a conducive atmosphere to support the student learning. In addition, they also take full responsibility for the partial development of student mental and personality to improve student attention and motivation.

Learning Methods

Teacher has capabilities to change the psyche and mindset of their students from not knowing to knowing (Brooks, 2008). To reach conducive interaction, teachers must implement suitable teaching methods to be adapted toward the student characteristics (Biggs, 2011). Every teacher has their effective teaching methods whereas every student has their adaptability to the teaching method (Biggs, 2011).

One of teaching methods which getting more popularity is discussion method. This involved of two or more participants to interact with each other to exchange opinions and maintains in problem solving to obtain agreement among them. Learning using discussion method is an interactive learning (Lundvall, 2010).

Discussion method can improve student in understanding the concepts and problem-solving skills. However, the use of the method of discussion results must be completed with demonstration for increasing the quantity of knowledge.

METHODOLOGY

Respondents And Sampling Technique

This study used stratified random sampling technique. It involved the population of groups called strata with a set of subjects more or less homogeneous. Since the study will observe the junior high school students as the respondents, then, they are grouped into three groups, namely the class-1, class-2, class-3. All the groups are participated in this study. This suggests that the knowledge of strata along with its properties is needed. Since each group is homogeneous population strata, the sample can be taken by simple random technique. The final sample is obtained by combining sub-sample of all strata.

Statistical Testing

It used Multiple Linear regression analysis and t-test. Both formulas are used to analyze the variable in this study. T-test has an objective to test the strength of the hypothesis proposed in this study. Both tests have a goal to find how emotional stability can be influential to the improvement of student achievement. To improve the accuracy, it also used f-test

(ANOVA) to know how the variable can influence other and get significant impact to increase student achievement.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Discussion

From the multiple linear regression analysis, it was obtained formula to predict the relationship of the dependent and independent variables such as students' emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method on student achievement as below.

$$Y = 3.769 + 0.154X_1 + 0.104X_2 + 0.154X_3 + e \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The analysis result showed that the value of a (constant) was 3769. It means that if there is no variable students' emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method, then student achievement (\hat{Y}) will be 3.769.

b. T-test

T-test has an objective to test the strength of the hypothesis proposed in this study. T-test result of simple linear regression is showed below.

H1: There is the influence of emotional stability on student achievement.

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis, the variable of student emotional stability obtained regression coefficient t value = 6.436 with a significance level of 0.000. By using the significance limit of 0.05, it obtained t-table of 0.676. This means that t-count is greater than t-table which means 1.381 is higher than 0.676 as the reason to reject H_0 and accept H_a . Therefore, the first research hypothesis (H1) can be accepted or proven. Direction of positive regression coefficient showed how student emotional stability has a significant positive effect on student achievement in mathematics and science. Emotional stability in this study can improve the student achievement.

H2: There is influence of parenting style on student achievement.

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis, the variables of parenting style regression coefficient values obtained for 0.104 and $t = 0.714$ with a significance level of 0.026. By using significance limit of 0.05, it obtained t-table 0.676. This means that t-count is greater than t-table, of $0.714 > 0.676$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Therefore, the second research hypothesis (H2) can be accepted and proven. The positive value in the regression coefficient means that parenting style has a significant positive effect on the improvement of student achievement. It means parenting style is influential in improving student achievement.

H3: There is the influence of teaching teachers to increase student achievement.

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis, the variable of teaching methods gives regression coefficient of 0.154 and $t = 1.398$ with significance level 0.012.

By using significance limit of 0.05, it obtained t-table 0.676. This means that t-count is greater than t-table, $1.398 > 0.676$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Therefore, the third research hypothesis (H3) can be accepted and proven. Direction way of positive regression coefficient means that teaching method has a significant positive effect on student achievement improvement. In other words, it can be concluded that how teacher deliver the lessons is important and influential in improving student achievement.

c. F-Test (ANOVA)

F test is to determine whether the variable of students' emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method simultaneously has significant influence to increase student achievement. F-test analysis results are given in Table 4.

Table 1. Test F Results ANOVA^b

<i>Model</i>		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	Regression	909.461	5	181.892	25.267	.000 ^a
1	Residual	820.664	114	7.199		
	Total	1730.125	119			

a. Predictors: (Constant), students emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method

b. Dependent Variable: student achievement

Source: analysis result of SPSS ver.16.00

Based on Table 1 in the top results of hypothesis testing, it gained significance level 5% and obtained F-count 25.267 and a significance of 0.000. While F tables as seen at a significance level of 5% by df numerator (k-2) and df denominator (nk) of the obtained F is $F(3: 114) = 2.68$. Therefore, df numerator (k-2) is larger than df denominator (nk), e.g. $25.267 > 2.68$ and significance limit $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a accepted. Thus, the fourth hypothesis (H_4) are accepted and proven. It also concluded that student emotional stability, parenting style and teaching method simultaneously has significant influence to increase student achievement.

CONCLUSION

There are positive influences of parenting style to increase student achievement as found in this study. It is also suggested by Baumrind, Teeven & McGhee (in Shaffer, 1994) that the way parents educate their children affected the children motivation. In the class setting, the children need more than motivation but also proper teaching approach to increase their class achievement. Combined with the role of parent in home will greatly affect the student achievement (Bradley, 2001). Since emotional stability also tested in this study, then it can complete our understanding that student adaptation to the surrounding environment with suitable teaching method. When children emotion is disturbed, it will degrade their learning achievement which impact on lower focus on learning and suboptimal school achievement. Student who is relatively free from distraction will have lower anxiety and other emotional disturbances as showed in this study. In addition, they will develop good concentration (Lecavalier, 2006).

Finally, since one aspect that determines the success of education is the learning process, teacher must repair their core educational process in order to deliver the lessons. In the implementation, teacher must find innovative way that is adaptable to student situation.

SUGGESTION

To improve student achievement, it needs the role of parents, teacher (school), communities in order to arrange innovative teaching method. This study found that teachers as educators are a critical success factor of educational endeavor. Therefore, school environment reform must be done to find better learning approach and higher teacher competence. This study has been

contributed to the discourse of student achievement and the significance role of teachers in education.

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